

varieties (results not presented). Few *O. glaberrima* varieties had the same reaction pattern.

These results suggest that numerous specific resistance genes are present in *O. glaberrima* some of them different from those found in *O. sativa*. Different combinations of these genes imply the diversity of reactions found.

The 32 resistant or intermediate varieties identified divide into two groups. TG10, BG155, BG162, BG178, YG12, YG15, YG247, YG304, and MG26 are resistant to all strains used. This means that these varieties have specific resistance genes, and that corresponding virulence genes are rare in the Ivory Coast pathogen population. The 23 varieties that scored 4 could carry a high level of general resistance. The genetic basis of that resistance should be studied. ■

Pest resistance – insects

Comparison of standard evaluation system and Oñate's method in assessing stalk-eyed fly resistance

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The stalk-eyed fly *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart is an indigenous dipterous rice stem borer found all over Africa. Infestation by the larva causes deadhearts.

We evaluated 27 rice genotypes against stalk-eyed fly during 1989 wet season—24 from Asia; one *O. sativa* (Koko) and one *O. glaberrima* from Africa; and standard susceptible check Suakoko 8. Adult flies collected in the field were released in a screenhouse sited in an irrigated ricefield at IITA.

Deadhearts were assessed by Oñate's method (normal practice in Africa) and *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) 45 and 60 d after transplanting (DT).

No variety was highly resistant (0 damage). ARC10331, Parakulam, and

Assessing rice resistance to SEF, using two methods. Nigeria, 1989 WS.

Genotype	Deadhearts (%) ^a			
	Method 1		Method 2	
	45 DT (X ± S.E.)	60 DT (X ± S.E.)	45 DT (X ± S.E.)	60 DT (X ± S.E.)
ARC 5823	16 ± 3	21 ± 3	16 ± 3	22 ± 3
ARC 5912	19 ± 3	24 ± 5	18 ± 3	25 ± 5
ARC 5989	18 ± 2	20 ± 3	18 ± 2	21 ± 3
ARC 6157	6 ± 2	12 ± 2	6 ± 2	12 ± 2
ARC 6619	17 ± 2	20 ± 4	17 ± 3	20 ± 4
ARC 6632	22 ± 2	34 ± 3	20 ± 2	31 ± 4
ARC 7255	11 ± 4	19 ± 5	11 ± 4	19 ± 5
ARC 10331	8 ± 3	5 ± 2	8 ± 3	5 ± 2
ARC 10660	15 ± 3	16 ± 2	15 ± 3	17 ± 3
Balam	91 ± 3	14 ± 2	9 ± 3	14 ± 3
Bhumansan	16 ± 3	16 ± 3	16 ± 3	16 ± 3
BG 276-5	14 ± 2	21 ± 3	13 ± 2	22 ± 3
BG 380	13 ± 3	25 ± 4	14 ± 3	27 ± 4
Chekhalopoiortal	13 ± 4	10 ± 4	11 ± 3	10 ± 4
CR57-MR 1523	11 ± 2	10 ± 2	10 ± 2	10 ± 2
Kakatiya	11 ± 4	11 ± 3	10 ± 3	11 ± 3
Moirangphou	10 ± 2	16 ± 2	10 ± 2	16 ± 2
Parakulam	6 ± 3	10 ± 3	5 ± 3	10 ± 3
Phodum	15 ± 3	16 ± 3	14 ± 3	16 ± 3
Rajendradhan	10 ± 3	11 ± 3	9 ± 3	11 ± 3
T10	16 ± 1	13 ± 2	16 ± 1	13 ± 2
T1477	14 ± 4	12 ± 2	14 ± 4	11 ± 2
<i>O. sativa</i> (Koko)	19 ± 3	33 ± 4	19 ± 3	33 ± 4
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	5 ± 3	8 ± 3	5 ± 3	9 ± 3
Suraksha	16 ± 2	14 ± 3	16 ± 2	14 ± 2
Vikramarya	11 ± 2	17 ± 2	11 ± 2	17 ± 2
Suakoko 8 (susceptible check)	34 ± 5	32 ± 4	33 ± 5	30 ± 4

^a Av of 10 replications. DT = days after transplanting. ^bPercentage deadhearts computed by *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) (1988). ^cPercentage deadhearts computed by Oñate (1965) method as:

$$X = P\bar{X}_{nz} 100$$

where

$$P = \frac{\text{number of affected hills}}{\text{number of hills in the plot (row)}}$$

$$\bar{X}_{nz} = \frac{\text{number of deadhearts}}{\text{number of tillers in the affected hills}}$$

O. glaberrima scored resistant (< 10% deadhearts) at 45 and 60 DT by both evaluation methods (see table). In all other varieties, more deadhearts were found at 60 DT than at 45 DT, probably because the flies were confined, and additional young tillers became susceptible as the plants

approached maximum tillering. Results of both evaluation methods were comparable at 45 and 60 DT. We recommend that screening be evaluated using SES. It is as precise as Oñate's method, and is easier and faster. Oñate's method is practical only when a few genotypes are screened. ■

Reactions of promising rice cultivars to gall midge (GM)

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is the most important pest of rice in

Vidarbha region, Maharashtra State. We screened 56 promising entries for resistance during 1987-89 wet seasons.

Entries were transplanted in 3-m-long rows spaced 20 cm apart. Total number of tillers and affected tillers (silvershoots) 50 d after transplanting were recorded on 10 hills selected randomly in each row. Ten entries were resistant (see table). ■